

ISLAM, IDENTITY, AND NATIONALISM: RELIGIOUS DIMENSIONS OF THE KURDISH STRUGGLE

Alsaba Bin Yamin

Research Scholar, Department of West Asian Studies and North African Studies
Aligarh Muslim University
Email: alsababinyamin@gmail.com

Mohammad Gulrez

Former Vice Chancellor, Aligarh Muslim University
Senior Professor, Department of West Asian Studies and North African Studies
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh
Email: mgulrez.wa@amu.ac.in

Abstract:

This paper attempts to probe the contribution of religion and religious figures in the formation of Kurdish nationalism. Interestingly, it seeks to find out how Kurdish Islamists deal with the conflict between nationalism and Islamism at the same time? The paper argues that Islamism and nationalism share a long history of being intertwined. For Kurdish Islamists—including Salafis—to retain their supporters, they must connect with Kurdish nationalism. However, they also support Kurdish statehood and think that Kurdish culture and identity are unique. Since 2014, the Kurdistan region of Iraq (KRI) has seen a further blending of Islamism and nationalism, which can be attributed to rising political pressures in the religious sphere following Daesh. By bureaucratizing Islam, appropriating Islamic leaders, and advancing Kurdish Islam, Kurdish government authorities meddle in religious matters. We contend that state co-optation of religion is both a means of gaining more influence over society and a step in the process of constructing a state and a nation. Our research employs an empirical method based on contextual and case-sensitive information to analyze the Kurdish situation.

Keyword: Kurdish Islam, Islamism, Salafism, religious nationalism, nation building, ethnic nationalism

Introduction

Kurds make a population of around 32 millions spread majorly across four adjacent countries of Turkey, Iran, Iraq and Syria. Though ethnically different and culturally rich, they remain one of the world's largest stateless people. In an everyday struggle for a separate homeland, they encounter states, pressure groups, militant/terrorist groups and, of course, a conflict within. While Kurdish struggle for an independent nation is often portrayed as secular, ethnicity-based, this paper argues that Islamic identity, via religious institutions, narratives and actors, has played significant yet underexamined role in shaping political consciousness, community cohesion and resistance strategies particularly in response to state oppression and regional fragmentation.

In August of 2014, the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) attempted to exterminate the Yazidis, a Kurdish ethnic group, from a Kurdish city in Iraq. Thousands of Kurds were massacred, starved to death, raped, or sold into slavery as hundreds of thousands of Kurds fled to the mountains to escape. ISIS seized hundreds of Kurdish communities in northern Syria in September 2014, a month later. The number of Kurds slain increased by thousands, and over 200,000 were displaced from their homes in search of safety. Before being freed by Kurdish forces at the end of January 2015, ISIS ruled much of Kobane for months.

However, the coalition bombings and ISIS's heavy weaponry destroyed 80% of Kobane. Sanitation, water supply, and electricity were all cut off from the city (BBC, 2014; Yildiz, 2014). Everyday basic services were and still are extremely limited, and food supplies are still insufficient. These continuous atrocities have compelled thousands of Kurdish refugees to escape their homelands in the Middle East in an effort to find safety outside the region and beyond the borders, as has happened time and time again throughout the twentieth and twenty-first centuries.

Statelessness has been acknowledged as a significant legal and political issue for many people worldwide since the creation of nation-states and the introduction of citizenship, passports, and legal documents. Many Palestinians, the Bidun in Kuwait and the Middle East, the Biharis in Bangladesh, the denationalized Kurds in Syria and other Middle Eastern nations, the Roma in central and south-east Europe, the Tamils in Sri Lanka, the Biharis in Bangladesh, the Haitians in the Dominican Republic, and a number of ethnic and social groups from the former

Soviet bloc, including the Russian minority in the Baltic states, are currently stateless groups (Lynch, 2005; Southwick and Lynch, 2009; Molnar and Gotazar, 2009).

Under the 1954 UN Convention, certain Kurds are legally regarded as stateless people. Law No. 93, issued in August 1962, which mandated an extraordinary census be conducted in the Hasakeh governorate, north-eastern Syria, resulted in the denial of citizenship to nearly 300,000 Kurds residing in Syria today. The official government justification for this census was to determine the number of individuals who had unlawfully crossed the border from Turkish Kurdistan after 1945 and to find "alien infiltrators" (Barr, 2011; Chulov, 2014).

120,000 Kurds, or 20% of the Syrian Kurdish population, officially lost their citizenship as a result of this regional initiative, which was closely linked to the state-sponsored Arabization drive. This was done in an effort to keep non-Arab minorities out of the country. Actually, this number was impacted by more than twice as many. Due to natural population growth, this figure has actually increased, with an estimated 750,000 Syrian Kurds lacking citizenship in 2011 (Altug, 2011). Basic rights like freedom of movement, education, political involvement, lawful marriage, and property ownership were denied to them. They had no recognized existence and the following generations must deal with the same problems when their children grow up. Children usually inherit their parents' and grandparents' statelessness, but many families were split up, with some family members obtaining citizenship with the use of bribes to Syrian government authorities and others failing to do so (Lynch and Ali, 2006).

Given this lengthy history of denaturalization and marginalization, it is noteworthy that many, but not all, of the Kurds who had been stateless in Syria for decades were awarded a sort of limited citizenship by the Bashar Al-Assad regime at the start of the 2011 Syrian civil war. This was not because the Syrian government's perception of Kurds had altered much. Instead, Al-Assad desperately needed support for his government and sought for secular Kurds to aid him in his fight against a number of religious organizations, such as ISIS, al-Nusra, al-Qa'ida, and the so-called Free Syrian Army.

However, not even the most basic minority rights, like the right to their culture or language, have been extended to Syria's new Kurdish citizens.

Kurds, whether or not they are officially considered Syrian "citizens," have a particularly hard time starting a business, buying or renting a property or a car, and inheriting or passing on their wealth to their children, according to people interviewed for this project who had previously lived in Syria before moving to the UK or Germany. Even Syrian Kurds who have recently received official documents still have trouble traveling overseas since many nations refuse to grant the visas that Syrian passport holders typically need.

The ongoing discrimination and lack of political, social or economic rights provide at least a partial explanation of why Kurds do not trust any of the factions in Syria, Turkey or elsewhere in the region, and want to create their own independent, or at least autonomous region (H.I. & E.Y., 2014).

Methodology

We have employed a qualitative methodology which is based purely on secondary data analysis, and is suitable for examining the religious dimensions of Kurdish identity and nationalism. The sources we reviewed include scholarly articles, books, party manifestos, political documents and media reports relevant to Kurdish society and its religious discourses. Through a comprehensive literature review, the study systematically synthesizes established research to identify key themes and theoretical debates on the role of Islam in Kurdish nationalism. We have further applied textual and content analysis to analyse published speeches, organizational statements, and religious writings to examine the ways in which identity and religious narratives are articulated and mobilized by Kurdish actors. We have also utilized a comparative historical analysis to contextualize developments across different regions and eras. This approach provides nuanced, context-rich understanding without reliance on primary data collection by triangulating insights from diverse sources. Such methodologies ensure the research to remain rigorous, transparent, and grounded in credible existing scholarship.

Historical background

Kurdish nationalism and their affiliation to Islam has always been contested. In Turkey, for example, there has long been discussion about religious intellectuals' propensity toward groupism. For example, in the

run-up to World War I, the Ottoman theologian Babanzade Ahmet Naim (1872–1934) was highly critical of the burgeoning Turkish republicanism, claiming that nationalism is totally forbidden in Islam. He maintained that its proponents were working to develop a substitute for the ummah as the fundamental social unit for Muslims around the world. However, this viewpoint was increasingly abandoned when the new Turkish nation-state arose from the ashes of empire.

For instance, the Turkish nationalist Ahmet Agayef (1869–1939) responded to Babanzade by arguing that the Quran speaks of the wrongness of tribalism rather than national awareness. He says that one of the main goals of the early Muslims was to bring the Arab nation together, citing chapter 9, verse 97, which criticizes the Bedouins' parochialism. Accordingly, Agayef believes that the development of the Arab national ideal, which is inherent in the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad, was essential to the spread of Islam (Agayef, 1919).

Turkish nationalism's founding father, Ziya Gökalp (1876–1924), made a similar case. He cited the well-known statement in Surat-al-Hujurat (verse 13) that various peoples were formed in order for them to know or recognize one another. He took this to signify that individuals should speak the languages of others, suggesting that there are valid national variations in the globe. This was further supported by chapter 10, verse 47, which stated that God sent a messenger to each of these countries or peoples. Gökalp therefore came to the conclusion that Islam supports modernizing nationalism and its goal of creating states made up of homogeneous nations, or the kind of mosaic that Brubaker had in mind.

In addition to playing a significant role in the establishment of the Turkish Republic, Agayef and Gökalp's religiously supported, timeless approach to ethnicity served as a major point of reference for the conservative nationalists who made up the core of the Turkish–Islamic synthesis in the 1990s. Islam is typically used in these discourses as a defense of national identity as well as a unique culture that was partially created by the Turkish people. The supposed foundation of Turkey's exceptionalism—its singular blend of secular unity and unstoppable popular religiosity—is this symbiotic relationship between an eternal Turkish nation (with deep prehistoric roots within the central Asian hinterland) and the rise of a great world faith.

The assumption that such an accommodation can only be maintained if all political traces of minority identity and religious practice are meticulously absorbed under a banalistic concept of Islamic brotherhood, where dissent has always been viewed as both un-Islamic and un-Turkish. As a result, the Kurds were urged to put aside their ethnic identity and join the Turks in a brotherhood where it was always clear who was the *abi* (a slang term for an older guy), according to one former PKK member.

In response, many Kurds have advocated for the Turkish government to give them greater recognition for their role in the growth of the Muslim world. For example, Altan Tan, a well-known Kurdish politician who supports Islam, has long charged that the Diyanet has a chauvinistically Turkish understanding of the religion and has betrayed the law of brotherhood. In a similar vein, Kurdish journalist İbrahim Sediyanı has advocated for the inclusion of more information about Kurdish civilization in Diyanet's textbooks, which still heavily emphasize Arab, Persian, and Turkish cultures (Sediyanı, 2014).

When recounting the views of the Kurdish local mullahs (*mele*), who often use their addresses to the Friday congregational prayer to accuse the state of preferring Turkish cultural supremacy, Zeki Sarıgil and Ömer Fazlıoğlu make a similar point. According to one such priest, "they say we are brothers..." But although one brother's language—Turkish—is allowed, the other is prohibited. What sort of fraternity is this? Others have reportedly pointed to a persistent trend toward *Hanafi* jurisprudence, which is the majority Turks' *madhab*, at the expense of *Shafi* practices, which are adhered to by the majority of Kurds.

However, a large number of Islamic academics have started to acknowledge Kurdish ethnicity and move away from the categorical rejection of non-Turkish cultural traditions since the AKP was elected. In other words, religious intellectuals' suggestions to change the conflict between the state and the PKK are no longer primarily based on the pervasive "Islamic brotherhood" narrative of the Turkish–Islamic synthesis. Instead, they have used Islamic justifications to support the notion that the nation's Kurds, like Turks, form a cohesive community with indisputable ethnic rights—a group, in Brubaker's terminology.

For example, theologian and writer Ali Bulaç has lately maintained that countries cannot be denied the freedom to express their cultures and

collective rights because language and skin color (qavm) are among Allah's ayah. Similarly, the preacher Mustafa İslamoğlu maintains that since the Quran defines such distinctions, submitting to a race does not contradict Islam's universality (Bulac, 2015).

He goes on to say that the devil is only responsible for the chauvinistic traits of pre-Islam, such as racism, tribalism, and uncivil nationalism. In a similar vein, Faruk Beşer of the Union of Turkish Ulema, an organization that collaborates closely with Diyanet, has maintained that it is improper from a religious perspective to subjugate the Kurds by envisioning a Turkey with a single race, nation, and language because Allah is the one who created social identities.

A similar argument is made by Hayrettin Karaman, a professor of Islamic law, who highlights the legitimate right of Turkey's minorities to preserve their uniqueness based on the dual markers of difference—culture (language) and biology (skin tone). According to him, the latter may legitimately influence religious behavior within a broad yet all-encompassing faith. He goes on to say that this is the difference between the ummah, which Karaman defines as the adherents of a religion and prophet, and what God refers to as a millet in the Quran. He contends that even if the former develops into a separate country, such a separation is acceptable (Karaman, 2009).

He gets to the conclusion that, in this sense, it is acceptable for a group of individuals who are connected by race or cultural customs to identify as a group and work toward the creation of a coterminous state—so long as this is done under a Muslim supra-identity.

Even the Diyanet, which has long favored concentrating only on the importance of fraternity and the damage that results from Muslim violence, has begun to acknowledge the ethnic distinctions between Turks and Kurds. For example, Mehmet Görmez, the current president, claimed in 2013 that the Quran claims that the ayahs of Allah are the reason for the linguistic differences. He goes on to say that rejecting this is equivalent to rejecting any other ayah of Allah and that it is a transgression against mankind and Allah to exclude or show contempt for a race, language, or skin color.

According to Brubaker, Görmez and the majority of Turkey's religious ulema are essentially bringing a group into being by doing this. These discourses are based on the idea that nations and races are significant

entities that are always present in Quranic terms and that continue to be the center of social agency, which is consistent with his three groupism characteristics. These also contain the fundamental premise that the Kurdish nation is internally consistent, that is, that the Kurds are consistently devoted to a mission of collective self-realization and, first, universally aware of their national identity.

Thus, it is positioned alongside other Arab, Turkish, and Persian things in the world as part of the type of mosaic of ethnic/cultural blocs that Brubaker finds in Western nationalisms. In the case of Turkey, the resulting group is likely to rely on some sort of future political devolution of power to the predominantly Kurdish southeast of the country. By emphasizing the earliest origins of institutions and the part that God played in their formation, accepting sub-ummah organizations is made into a sort of religious obligation, which negates objections and increases the immanent power of what Brubaker refers to as "ethnopolitical entrepreneurs.

Kurdish nationalists have undoubtedly benefited from this change in attitude. The PKK has started to abandon its long-standing claim that Islam is to blame for the growth of linguistic and cultural subordination. The notion that religion has had an anaesthetic effect on Kurdish-speaking people in the region—as its founder, Abdullah Öcalan, put it—and so contributed to the Arab and Turkish cultural hegemony has begun to wane(Öcalan, 1993).

The AKP's appeal to popular religiosity was more popular than the PKK's secularism in most south-eastern provinces by the 2004 local elections. In fact, the PKK's national vote dropped from 2 million in 2002 to 1.6 million in 2007, and by the 2011 general elections, it was still losing at least half of its wards to the AKP in important Kurdish provinces like Diyarbakır, Bitlis, Muş, Van, and Mardin. This has encouraged Öcalan's organization to become even more in line with the theologians' discourse.

As a result, the PKK's strategy has gradually changed. Beginning with Öcalan's book, *A Revolutionary Approach to the Question of Religion (Din Sorununa Devrimci Yaklaşım)*, in the 1990s, and continuing with the creation of ethnicized religious groups like the Islamic Union of Kurdistan (Kürdistan İslami Hareketi) and the Union of Kurdistan Patriot Imams (Kürdistan Yurtsever İmamlar Birliği), the PKK acknowledged that

it might be necessary to use religion as part of what it referred to as the anti-colonial struggle. The PKK started hosting Islamic funerals and mawlid for guerrilla martyrs in the 2000s; imams started to attend its public gatherings more frequently; congregational prayers were held outside state-run mosques as a protest tactic; and religious festivals were given more importance.

The Quran's chapter 30, verse 22, which reads, "The difference of your languages and colors is among the ayah of Allah," served as the banner for a 2014 Democratic Islam Congress organized by Öcalan. He called attendees his brothers in Islam in his vicarious welcome speech, and he wrapped up by talking about God-given protections for communities' rights to keep their native culture and speak their mother tongue. Other well-known individuals agreed, including the Kurdish Members of Parliament Altan Tan and Ahmet Türk, who claimed that Kurds are the actual natives of the Anatolian heartland and are more pious Muslims than their fellow citizens.

The longstanding and potent notion that a unique and everlasting Kurdish people gave up their right to become a nation for the sake of religious unity following the fall of the Ottoman Empire is one of the main reasons for this shift toward using Islam more and more to legitimize ethno-nationalist rhetoric. The claim that the Kurds adopted Islam at least two centuries before the Turks and were among the first nations to formally choose Muslim rule following the divinely selected Arabs is frequently invoked. According to Öcalan, the major empires that have occupied Kurdistan have purposefully obfuscated this fundamental fact of history.

He encouraged Altan Tan to uncover and spread the hidden Islam that he feels is buried beneath the cultural mask that imperial powers have imposed during a meeting in February 2013. He clarified that the ultimate goal is to eliminate these adulterations, return society to a more authentic moral foundation, and—possibly most importantly—restore the Kurdish nation's unity.

Formation of Kurdish religious identity

Kurdish society has been profoundly impacted by Islam; it has shaped even seemingly secular facets of social and political life. Networks of madrasas and sufi orders have served as social integration tools, bridging segmentary divides, just as in other tribal communities. It should come

as no surprise that the concept of a Kurdish national identity initially surfaced in the madrasa setting, where students from all around Kurdistan came together and where the Kurdish language was taught in addition to Arabic and Persian. The madrasa was closely linked to the earliest poets whose poetry reflected pride in Kurdish ancestry, and it was via the madrasa networks that their writings were disseminated and gained recognition. Sufi orders fostered unity that transcended regional and tribal boundaries. Nearly all of the initial Kurdish uprisings with a nationalist bent were headed by Sufi shaykhs.

Kurdish society's historical encounters with Islamic doctrines and practices, as well as with Muslim nations that integrated sections of Kurdistan, gave rise to the unique character of Islam in Kurdistan. The conflict between orthodoxy and heterodoxy, which is present everywhere, is especially noticeable in Kurdistan.

The few major centers in Kurdistan, including Cizre, Arbil, and Amid (Diyarbakir), were quickly assimilated into the Islamic world of scholarship and civilization after Islam reached the Kurds in its early stages of spread. However, due to its hilly terrain, the majority of Kurdistan stayed on the periphery of this world and had a conflicted relationship with orthodox, scholarly Islam. On the one hand, even the most remote locations saw the emergence of some centers of traditional Islamic education. On the other hand, groups and individuals who were persecuted for political or religious reasons sought safety in this physical setting, which allowed heterodox religious communities to endure the longest (Bruinessen, 1999).

As a result, Kurdistan paradoxically became both the home to some of the most heterodox populations in the Middle East and a center of rigorous Sunni orthodoxy, subscribing to the Shafi'i school of law rather than the more liberal Hanafi school that was embraced by the majority of the surrounding Arabs and Turks. The religions of Ahl-i Haqq and Yezidi originated in southern and central Kurdistan, respectively. While the former has only ever had Kurdish supporters, the latter has gained widespread acceptability among Iran's other ethnic groups; yet, it is only in Kurdistan that it continues to thwart attempts to further islamise it. There are significant parallels between the Yezidis and the Ahl-i Haqq and the beliefs and customs of the Kizilbash or Alevis of modern-day

Turkey. The Kurdish communities among the Alevis are generally more disassociated from Islamic orthodoxy than the Turkish ones.

Sufi order and their social and political role

Kurdistan has a strong presence of Sufi organizations, and the Sufi shaykh may be a better representation of Kurdish Islam than the legal expert. Sufis made up the majority of the most well-known ulama in Kurdish history, and several of them gained significant political clout. Although there were several Sufi organizations in Kurdistan at one point or another, the Qadiriyya and the Naqshbandiyya have dominated the scene for the last few centuries (Akyuz, 1990).

From one perspective, a Sufi order functions similarly to an unofficial school, providing a standardized set of spiritual exercises and mystical techniques that the novice does under the supervision of an experienced teacher. Although these methods were created by the orders' founders, they are thought to be based on lessons that the Prophet himself taught orally. Known as murshid (guide) or shaykh in Kurdistan, these activities are only taught by the most proficient mystics. It is not an informal title; a written certificate (ijaza) from one's own teacher is the only way to become a shaykh; lengthy instruction under the master's guidance is merely one requirement; an ijaza is not granted automatically.

In Kurdistan, a shaykh may have followers from a variety of backgrounds. The most devout followers (murid) participate in daily group recitations and meditations and reside with the shaykh, either in his home, a zawiya (dervish convent), or as near to him as feasible. The shaykh or his representative (khalifa) leads a broader group of murids who have also been inducted into the order and gather more or less frequently for group devotions. Typically, shaykhs who have murids who live far away designate one or more khalifas from their most accomplished followers (Bruinessen, 2011).

Although a considerably larger number of followers are drawn to the shaykh's charm, they may not even be initiated into the order and do not actively participate in the mystical exercises. Many shaykhs carry out pastoral and thaumaturgic duties, in contrast to ulama. They serve as healers of physical and mental ailments, mediate disputes amongst kin, and are consulted on moral and political issues. They are thought to have the ability to intercede with God and to provide blessings simply by being there.

Throughout Kurdistan, the role of shaykh has tended to be inherited. There are just two families of Qadiri shaykhs in Southern Kurdistan: the Talabani and the Barzinji. Because many people who were not the sons of shaykhs were granted *ijazah* (a certificate or permission given by a qualified teacher), the Naqshbandi order quickly grew in the early 19th century, in part at the expense of the Qadiriyya. Having studied under one of the greatest Indian Naqshbandi teachers, the charismatic Mawlana Khalid, a Kurd from the Sulaymaniya region, trained a large number of disciples and appointed well over thirty shaykhs to various parts of Kurdistan (in addition to an even larger number of khalifas appointed to other parts of the Ottoman Empire).

However, the propensity for hereditary shaykhhood also manifested among Kurdish Naqshbandis in the subsequent generations. Consequently, several of the orders' branches became nearly tribes. The Barzanis are arguably the most extreme illustration of this phenomenon. Some of the followers of the Barzan shaykhs were tribal, but the majority were non-tribal peasants who had either already established in or were close to the Barzan shaykhs' settlement. Although the society set itself apart with its strong egalitarianism and readiness to accept strangers as members, it eventually began acting more and more like a tribe as a result of conflicts with the nearby tribes (Bruinessen, 2011).

In the early half of the 19th century, the Naqshbandi order not only grew quickly but also gained political significance. In several regions of Kurdistan, Naqshbandi shaykhs held influential positions by the end of the century. This has nothing to do with other significant political events of the time. Administrative reforms during the first decades of the century eliminated the last autonomous Kurdish principalities and placed all of Kurdistan under the control of centrally appointed administrators. These governors could not control tribal disputes the way the Kurdish emirs had, and they lacked the moral power that the emirs possessed.

However, the Sufi orders have faced harsh criticism this century from a variety of sources, including Kurdish nationalist intellectuals, secular politicians focused on modernization, and Muslim reformists. The orders as they operated in Kurdistan, the superstitious and magical practices that were connected to them, and the unreasonable worship of hereditary shaykhs were all repudiated by Said Nursi, whose teachers included a Naqshbandi shaykh and whose own writings exude a mystical spirit (Bruinessen, 1992).

Religious versus ethnic Nationalism

For decades, academics have been perplexed by the connection between nationalism and religion. The importance of religion in the formation and maintenance of national identity was mainly overlooked by conventional nationalism studies until the 1990s (Anderson, 1991; Breuilly, 1993; Gellner, 1983; Hechter, 1975; Hobsbawm, 1990; Kedourie, 1960; Nairn, 1977). This oversight resulted from the secular replacement model, which viewed nationalism as an alternative to traditional faiths as a means of identification (Smith, 2000). At first, modern interpretations of religion believed that secularization would make religion obsolete (Berger, 1967, 1969; Bruce, 1996, 2002; Wilson, 1983). This secularist attitude has been contested by recent research, which has also brought attention to the connection between nationalism and religion (Asad, 2003; Brubaker, 2012; Eastwood & Prevalakis, 2010; Friedland, 2001, 2002; Gorski, 2000, 2006; Hastings, 1997; Juergensmeyer, 1993, 2000; Piscatori, 1986; Rieffer, 2003; Safran, 2003; Smith, 2000, 2003; Spohn, 2003; Van der Veer, 1994; Zubrzycki, 2006).

Though there is still a lack of thorough conceptual and theoretical understanding, investigations into how religion affects nationalism have attracted more attention. A significant amount of research has been done to comprehend how nationalist and religious statements interact. Examples include how Pietism shaped German identity (Avraham, 2019; Lehmann, 1982; Shantz, 2013). The construction of Hindu and Muslim nationalism in India (Van der Veer, 1994).

According to a number of studies, Islam has strengthened nationalism claims among Muslim populations, including Bosnian Muslims after Yugoslavia's dissolution (Babuna, 2004), Bengali Muslim nationalism (Khan, 1985), Muslim separatism in the Philippines (McKenna, 1998), the Hindu–Muslim conflict during the partition of India (Robinson, 2000) and in Kashmir (Sikand, 2001; Tremblay, 1996) and the Palestinian diaspora in Jordan (Vicente Pèrez, 2014).

According to some research, the effect of Islamic brotherhood and Muslim unity between Kurds and Turks may be waning. Due to the lack of a widely recognized interpretation, Islam never created a unified political collectivity among Turks and Kurds, who instead saw it through their ethnopolitical lenses (Soleimani, 2016). It is no longer able to unite Muslim Turks and Kurds and has ceased to function as a supranational

identity(Türkmen, 2021). Kurds frequently come into contact with secular co-ethnic actors who have taken a more accepting position toward Islam as they withdraw from Turkish Islamic organizations(Al, 2019; Sarigil & Fazlioglu, 2013; Sarigil & Karakoc, 2016). Those who mistrust the Brotherhood and are making peace with secular Kurds are increasingly adopting Kurdish Islam(Gurses, 2015).

Kurdish mobilization has not decreased as a result of Turkey's Islamization under the Justice and Development Party (AKP) (Gurses & Ozturk, 2020); rather, it serves as a tool for the government to keep the Kurds in check (Kurt, 2019).

Kurdish nationalism did not explicitly associate itself with Islam until far into the 1980s, following the Shaykh Sa'id uprising. All the Kurdish cultural associations and political parties that arose were resolutely secular, despite the fact that the Sunni Kurds were generally more patriotic than Alevis, Ahl-i Haqq, Yezidis, and Shiites, and that the majority of Sunni Kurds were personally devout Muslims. On the other hand, Kurds who were active as devout Muslims downplayed their Kurdish ethnic identity and frequently clashed with the Kurdish movement, which was heavily influenced by Marxism, particularly from the 1950s onward. Islam has only become a major element in Kurdish politics again after Marxism's decline as a political force, and Kurdish identity politics have returned to Islamism(Bruinessen, 1986).

Despite its indirect effects, the Iranian revolution undoubtedly had a significant role in this process. Iran's Kurds were not organized in the early months of the revolution, and some religious figures, such as Mulla Izzaddin Husayni in Mahabad and Ahmad Muftizade, a scholar trained in Azhar, in Sanandaj, became their spokespersons. However, secular Kurdish politicians who had just returned from prison or exile and were successful in reorganizing the dormant (secular and left-leaning) Kurdish parties soon took over the leadership of the populace and control of events from these religious leaders.

Incidentally, Husayni had sided with the radical left early on and embraced an Islamic socialist populist rhetoric that placed a high value on the numerous ethnolinguistic groups in Iran having the right to self-determination. Short-lived Sunni Kurdish resistance movements were led by a brother of Husayni in Bane and by the Naqshbandi shaykh Osman in the Hawraman region when the new central government sent its army and Shi'i irregulars to seize control of Kurdistan. However, only

the secular forces remained in place when the guerrilla war started in earnest.

Ethnicity is meaningless, according to the Islamic movement's prevailing viewpoint. As a result, ethnic nationalism and all types of ethnic discrimination were to be condemned. However, at least in Turkey, national and ethnic identities have pushed themselves on the Islamic movement since the 1980s. On the one hand, right-wing Turkish nationalism has tried to appropriate Islamism by claiming that the Turkish-Islamic synthesis is the new state philosophy. People with pan-Turk ancestry rose to prominence in the Islamist Refah party, and Fethullah Gülen's powerful Nurcu movement branch not only adopted a distinctively Turkish nationalist rhetoric but also extended its operations throughout Turkic Central Asia.

Instead, this might only compel Kurdish Islamists to take back their unique identity within the Islamic movement. In the sense that religious-political organizations have grown in prominence and that even secular political forces have been forced to recognize and respect Islam, Kurdish culture and politics have become increasingly Islamic. However, compared to earlier times, Islamic activities in Kurdistan have become more overtly Kurdish.

For many years, quietist Salafism has been steadily gaining popularity in Kurdistan. Dr. Abdullatif Salafi, a Salafi sheikh in Sulaimaniyah, is the most well-known scholar of them all. Abdullatif Salafi, who comes from a devout family and was born in Ranya in the northern part of the Sulaimaniyah governorate, is an example of a scholar who does not challenge the authority (Abdullatif Salafi, interview, November 2018). He preaches support for the current Muslim rulers, just like other quietist Salafis (see Meijer Citation 2017 and Bonnefoy Citation 2017 for more on the apoliticism of quietist Salafis). As a result, Abdullatif was a useful government ally in the battle against Daesh as well as the Islamist opposition groups in KRI.

In the city of Sulaimaniyah, Abdullatif owns a mosque with a Qur'anic school and the well-known TV station Amozghary, which was founded in 2013. Regarding how to interact with the Kurdish authorities, Abdullatif and the Islamist political groups in Kurdistan hold divergent opinions (JalJalal, 2019). Pro-government and pro-status quo, Abdullatif advises his supporters to be more cautious, patient, and to maintain

stability rather than to protest. Islamist political parties had a decline in support during the same time that Abdullatif's popularity rose (Hadi Ali, interview, Head of the Leadership Council of KIU, March 2020). Thus, Kurdish Islamism is growing more and more in line with the government as quietist Salafism gains ground.

Kurdish Islam : adding a new dimension to universal Islam

Alongside the co-optation and repressive measures, the government gave emerging Islamic intellectuals who were putting out concrete alternatives to radical Islam—Kurdish Islam, for example—more media attention. Kurdish Islam, in our opinion, is Kurdish religious nationalism that has supplanted mainstream Kurdish nationalism and aids Kurdish political authorities in reaching as many voters as possible. In other words, Kurdish Islam is a story and discourse that the government in Iraqi Kurdistan promotes to its Islamic constituents.

In the 1990s, the notion that Kurdish Islam differs from Turkish and Arab Islam emerged. In order to denigrate the Kurdishness of the Islamist political parties, such as KIU, the Islamic Group, and the Islamic Movement, KDP and PUK politicians frequently used the term "Kurdish Islam" during their war against Kurdish Islamist parties in the 1990s. One analyst claims that the politicians adopted it in response to the Muslim Brotherhood and other religious revivals that arose in the Islamic world (Tahsin Hama Gharib, interview, March 2020). By highlighting the notion that these groups' experiences were fundamentally rooted in Arabic culture and thus foreign to Kurdish culture, they sought to undermine Islamist parties.

As Kurdistan's state-like institutions developed over the years, politicians persisted in using the phrase "Kurdish Islam". Kurdish authorities saw Kurdish Islam as a counterbalance to extremist militancy. The Kurdish political establishment's narrative is that Islamist extremism, which is so pervasive among Iraqi Arabs, is prevented by the Kurdish ethnic cause.

The Kurdish Islam discourse, in our opinion, is specifically aimed at the Kurdish Islamic community (not at the broader Kurdish populace, who are already nationalist, but rather at the more fervent believers). To put it another way, the Kurdish political establishment continues to use the same (nationalist) rhetoric while speaking to the broader population.

Additionally, they have recently introduced a discourse tailored to the Islamic community, utilizing multiple registers simultaneously (mainstream nationalist, religious nationalist/Islamic). In an effort to present Iraqi Kurdistan as a more liberal, accepting culture ready to form alliances with the West, the Kurdish Islam discourse is also aimed at Western capitals.

The story of Kurdish Islam attracted attention in Western capitals following the rise of Daesh in Iraq and Syria in 2014. The moderate and tolerant character of Kurdish Islam, or how Islam is practiced in KRI, is frequently highlighted by KRG. In contrast to an otherwise "violent" and chaotic Arab Iraq, KRG depicts the area as a peaceful oasis. In an attempt to fortify their common identity and forge a new, distinct national identity, de facto organizations (or entities seeking recognition) have broader policies that can be used to justify the promotion of Kurdish Islam (Kolstø and Blakkisrud, 2008; Caspersen, 2012). This is what Kolstø and Blakkisrud (2008) call an attempt by intellectuals, state leaders, and others to give an entity the characteristics of a nation-state. Cultural and linguistic homogenization is one of the policies implemented by de facto state authority.

The role of nationalizing religion in this process has received very little analysis and conceptualization. For instance, Caspersen ignores the importance of religion in creating internal legitimacy and broadening support for the independence movement in her research on nation-building and internal legitimacy in de facto states (Caspersen, 2012, 2015). Furthermore, since 2014, a new generation of independent scholars with government-aligned agendas has emerged, including theologian and novelist Tahsin Hama Gharib and TV Islamic preacher Abdulrahman Saddiq. In view of Kurdish national objectives, they also aim to reformulate Islam. We examine their claims in light of broader Kurdish and regional political developments in the next section.

For a long time, only the administration used the term Kurdish Islam to disparage the Islamist opposition groups. Tahsin Hama Gharib, a professor of law and politics at the University of Human Development in Sulaimaniyah, was the first scholar to introduce the term Kurdish Islam in 2003. Gharib argued that Islamic practices had to be applied in a way that supports the Kurdish independence movement. He believes that the "Kurdisation of Islam" is essential to strengthening Kurdistan's sense of

national identity. Kurdish Islam, which blends religion and Kurdish culture (as well as the Kurdish desire for independence), should form the foundation of the Kurdish statehood movement. "Kurdish Islam" is the label for this mix (Tahsin Hama Gharib, interview, March 2020).

Kurdish intellectuals and academics make up Gharib's audience. He describes Kurdish Islam as having four pillars: Sufism and spirituality; philosophy; cooperation and coexistence with the existing Kurdish authorities (i.e., Kurdish Islam is not political); and active individual participation, energy, and passion. All four pillars are evaluated in relation to his (simplified, some would argue warped) conception of Arab Islam, which is a political Islam in which people are purportedly less tolerant, non-spiritual, docile, and primarily concerned with adhering to Shari'a (Tahsin Hama Gharib, interview, March 2020).

It may be argued that Gharib's perspective on Kurdish Islam is more about reformulating nationalism than Islam. He contends that Kurdish intellectuals have so far adopted the European model, making the community shallow by failing to consider its deeper aspects. For example, the spiritual aspect of Kurdish poetry is unimportant to them. However, the Kurdish "experience must have a spiritual component in order to be effective" (Tahsin Hama Gharib, interview, March 2020). Kurdish Islam ought to serve as "a springboard to revive the modern concept of nationalism," according to Gharib (Tahsin Hama Gharib, interview, March 2020).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates how, since 2014, nationalism and Islamism have become more hybridized due to fresh political pressures in the religious sphere following Daesh. It addressed two related questions: 1) How do Kurdish Islamists deal with the challenge of simultaneously relating to Islamism and nationalism? 2) What are the reasons behind the efforts made by Kurdish authorities in Iraq to consolidate authority over religious activities since 2014? The paper answers these questions by showing that Kurdish Islamists, even Salafis, must relate to Kurdish nationalism to maintain their followers. Not only do they act pragmatically to garner popular support, but they also have faith in the Kurdish cause, which is embodied in the Kurdish aspiration for a Kurdish nation-state. Islamists may reject the notion of a distinct

"Kurdish Islam," but they support Kurdish statehood, are proud to be Kurds, and believe in the uniqueness of Kurdish culture and identity.

Kurdish political authorities increasingly intervene in the religious arena, including bureaucratising Islam, co-opting Islamic figures and by pushing a form of Islam that they believe serves their political goals. In recent years, Kurdish authorities in Iraq have promoted what they call 'Kurdish Islam' as an alternative to extremist Islamism. 'Kurdish Islam' is a kind of Kurdish religious nationalism. It is not an alternative for Kurdish mainstream nationalism, but co-exists with it. The 'Kurdish Islam' discourse is directed by the state at the Kurdish Islamist groups, in an attempt to make them more nationalist.

The report also indicates that while Kurdish authorities pioneered the first use of the term Kurdish Islam, it has in recent years been extended to independent scholars and intellectuals. These are not supported by the government, but the government provides them attention and official endorsement. However, many Kurdish Islamists firmly deny the nomenclature of Kurdish Islam.

The findings and analyses of this research contribute to the literature on state and nation-building in de facto states or entities that seek de jure independence, and how the leaders and intellectuals of these entities try to align the dominant religion of the population with ethnic and nationalist interests. Through Kurdistan, this study investigates the overlooked role of the nationalisation of religion in the growth and process of both state and nation-building in de facto independent entities. The idea of Kurdish Islam as the spirit of state-building is in accordance with the attempts of the de facto state authorities striving to detach themselves from their parent (or base) states (Caspersen, 2012; Richard and Smith, 2015).

Notes and References

- Al, S. (2019). Islam, ethnicity and the state: Contested spaces of legitimacy and power in the Kurdish-Turkish public sphere. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 19(1), 119–137.
- Altuğ, S. (2011). *Sectarianism in the Syrian Jazira: Community, land and violence in the memories of World War I and the French Mandate (1915–1939)* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Utrecht University, The Netherlands.

- Anderson, B. (1991). *Imagined communities: Reflections on the origin and spread of nationalism*. Verso.
- Asad, T. (2003). *Formations of the secular*. Stanford University Press.
- Avraham, D. (2019). German neo-pietism and the formation of national identity. *Church History*, 88(1), 87–119.
- Babuna, A. (2004). The Bosnian Muslims and Albanians: Islam and nationalism. *Nationalities Papers*, 32(2), 287–321.
- Berger, P. L. (1969). *A rumor of angels: Modern society and the rediscovery of the supernatural*. Anchor (Vol. 715). Garden City, NY: Doubleday.
- Breuilly, J. (1993). *Nationalism and the state*. Manchester University Press.
- Brubaker, R. (2012). Religion and nationalism: Four approaches *. *Nations and Nationalism*, 18(1), 2–20.
- Bruce, S. (1996). *Religion in the modern world: From cathedrals to cults*. Oxford University Press.
- Bruinessen, M. van. (1999). *The Kurds and Islam* (Working Paper No. 13). Islamic Area Studies Project.
- Bulac, A. (2015). *Turkey's democracy saga: The struggle against interventionist politics*. Paramus Publishing.
- Caspersen, N. (2012). *Unrecognized states: The struggle for sovereignty in the modern international system*. Polity Press.
- Eastwood, J., & Prevalakis, N. (2010). Nationalism, religion, and secularization: An opportune moment for research. *Review of Religious Research*, 52(1), 90–111.
- Friedland, R. (2001). Religious nationalism and the problem of collective representation. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 27(1), 125–152.
- Friedland, R. (2002). Money, sex, and god: The erotic logic of religious nationalism. *Sociological Theory*, 20(3), 381–425.
- Gellner, E. (1983). *Nations and nationalism*. Cornell University Press.
- Gorski, P. S. (2000). The mosaic moment: An early modernist critique of modernist theories of nationalism. *American Journal of Sociology*, 105(5), 1428–1468.
- Gurses, M. (2015). Is Islam a cure for ethnic conflict? Evidence from Turkey. *Politics and Religion*, 8(1), 135–154.
- Gurses, M. (2018). *Anatomy of a civil war: Sociopolitical impacts of the Kurdish conflict in Turkey*. University of Michigan Press.
- Hastings, A. (1997). *The construction of nationhood: Ethnicity, religion and nationalism*. Cambridge University Press.

- Hechter, M. (1975). *Internal colonialism: The Celtic fringe in British national development, 1536–1966* (Vol. 197). Univ of California Press.
- Hobsbawm, E. J. (1990). *Nations and nationalism since 1780: Program myth, reality*. Cambridge University Press.
- Juergensmeyer, M. (1993). *The new cold war?: Religious nationalism confronts the secular state*. University of California Press.
- Juergensmeyer, M. (2000). *Terror in the mind of god: The global rise of religious violence*. University of California Press.
- Kedourie, E. (1960). *Nationalism*. Praeger.
- Khan, Z. R. (1985). Islam and Bengali nationalism. *Asian Survey*, 25(8), 834–851.
- Kolstø, P., & Blakkisrud, H. (2008). Living with non-recognition: State- and nation-building in South Caucasian quasi-states. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 60(3), 483–509.
- Kurt, M. (2019). ‘My Muslim Kurdish brother’: Colonial rule and Islamist governmentality in the Kurdish region of Turkey. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 21(3), 350–365.
- Lehmann, H. (1982). Pietism and nationalism: The relationship between Protestant revivalism and national renewal in nineteenth-century Germany. *Church History*, 51(1), 39–53.
- Lynch, M. (2005). *Lives on hold: The human cost of statelessness*. Refugees International.
- Lynch, M., & Ali, P. (2006). *Buried alive: Stateless Kurds in Syria*. Refugees International. <https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b3840.html>
- McKenna, T. M. (1998). *Muslim rulers and rebels: Everyday politics and armed separatism in the southern Philippines* (Vol. 26). Univ of California Press.
- Molnár, T. (2012). Remembering the forgotten: Legal status of stateless persons under international law and EU law. In C. Gortázar (Ed.), *European migration and asylum policies: Coherence or contradiction?* (pp. 822–848). Bruylant.
- Nairn, T. (1977). *The break-up of Britain* (Vol. 2021). Verso Books.
- Öcalan, A. (1992). *Kadın ve aile sorunu*. Melsa Yayınları.
- Piscatori, J. P. 1986. *Islam in a world of nation-states*. Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Richards, R., & Smith, R. (2015). Playing in the sandbox: State building in the space of non-recognition. *Third World Quarterly*, 36(9), 1717–1735.
- Rieffer, B. A. J. (2003). Religion and nationalism: Understanding the consequences of a complex relationship. *Ethnicities*, 3(2), 215–242.

- Robinson, O. C. (2014). Sampling in interview-based qualitative research: A theoretical and practical guide. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11(1), 25–41.
- Safran, W. (2003). *The secular and the sacred: Nation, religion, and politics*. Psychology Press.
- Sarigil, Z., & Fazlioglu, O. (2013). Religion and ethno-nationalism: Turkey's Kurdish issue. *Nations and Nationalism*, 19(3), 551–571.
- Sarigil, Z., & Karakoc, E. (2016). Who supports secession? The determinants of secessionist attitudes among Turkey's Kurds. *Nations and Nationalism*, 22(2), 325–346
- Shantz, D. H. (2013). *An introduction to German pietism: Protestant renewal at the dawn of modern Europe*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Sikand, Y. (2001). Changing course of Kashmiri struggle: From national liberation to Islamist jihad? *Economic and Political Weekly*, 36(3), 218–227.
- Smith, A. D. (2000). The sacred dimension of nationalism. *Millennium: Journal of International Studies*, 29(3), 791–814.
- Soleimani, K. (2016). *Islam and competing nationalisms in the Middle East, 1876-1926*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Spohn, W. (2003). Multiple modernity, nationalism and religion: A global perspective. *Current Sociology*, 51(3–4), 265–286.
- Tremblay, R. C. (1996). Nation, identity and the intervening role of the state: A study of the secessionist movement in Kashmir. *Pacific Affairs*, 69(4), 471–497.
- Türkmen, G. (2021). *Under the banner of Islam: Turks, Kurds, and the limits of religious unity*. Oxford University Press.
- Van der Veer, P. (1994). *Religious nationalism: Hindus and Muslims in India*. University of California Press.
- Vicente Pérez, M. (2014). Between religion and nationalism in the Palestinian diaspora. *Nations and Nationalism*, 20(4), 801–820.
- Wilson, B. (1983). *Religion in sociological perspective*. Oxford University Press.
- Zubrzycki, G. (2006). *The crosses of Auschwitz: Nationalism and religion in post-communist Poland*. University of Chicago Press.